

A Study to Assess the Closed Incisional Negative Pressure Wound Therapy at Flap Suture Line: A Retrospective Study**Puja Priyadarshini**

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract**Aim:** The aim of the present study was to assess the closed Incisional Negative Pressure Wound Therapy at Flap Suture Line.**Material & Methods:** A retrospective analysis for the duration of 12 months of patients who underwent ciNPWT at the flap suture line was included in the study at department of Plastic Surgery. 30 patients were included in the study.**Results:** There were no significant differences between the two groups in terms of patient baseline information such as age, gender, ASA classification, and preoperative laboratory indices (including haemoglobin, alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase, creatinine, prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, and D-dimer). Within the NPWT group, all patients obtained scores below 20 score. Conversely, within the Control group, a significant majority of patients demonstrated ASEPSIS scores surpassing 20 score. There was no statistical difference in ADLS scores, LEFS scores, and VAS scores between the two groups.**Conclusion:** Closed incisional NPWT decreases the untoward effects of dead space following the reconstruction of complex wounds. The incidence of SSI and wound gaping can be reduced.**Keywords:** Closed Incisional Negative Pressure Wound Therapy, Wound Healing, Wound Dehiscence.

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Introduction

Flaps play a crucial role in the wound healing of critical wounds in which implants, bone, neurovascular structure, or vital viscera are exposed. [1] Incisional wound healing is an orchestra of biological and molecular events such as cell migration, proliferation and of extracellular matrix storing and remodelling. Certain pathophysiological and metabolic conditions can alter this healing milieu and thereby impair or delay healing. [2] Persistent dead space following flap cover is a frequently encountered challenge. It may lead to a hematoma, seroma, wound infection, and wound dehiscence. Wound dehiscence may be a devastating complication. Wound dehiscence in the postoperative period is an important outcome measure since it impacts the mortality, morbidity, duration of hospital stay.1 Surgical site infection (SSI), anemia, hypoproteinemia, tobacco abuse, diabetes are few of the important suboptimal wound factors which contribute to wound dehiscence. [1]

Risk factors used to assess surgical wounds' post-operative complications risk can be classified as trauma-related (soft tissue injury or fracture, type) surgery-related (incision placement, surgical site

contamination, technique, operative time, estimated blood loss) or patient-related (morbid obesity, multiple significant comorbidities, drugs, nicotine abuse). [3]

Methods to close an incision may range from sutures [4] to nitinol staples, adhesive strips, liquid skin adhesive [5] or a combination thereof. The management of clean, closed surgical incisions diversify from preoperative prophylactic precautions as well as microbial sealants, [6] intra-operative devices like prophylactic gentamycin-collagen sponges [7] to post-operative measures. Post-operative measures range from conventional dressing of sterile dry gauzes, [8] debriding agents and topical antimicrobial dressing, to more advanced wound dressings in an effort to stimulate the proliferative phase of wound healing, including hydrocolloids, [8] topical application of autologous blood products, [9] growth factors, [10] cultured skin [11] and Negative Pressure Wound Therapy (NPWT). [12,13,14] Negative pressure wound therapy (NPWT) is one of the proven treatments for wound healing of the suture site. [15,16] NPWT promotes wound healing in the closed suture site by removing fluid from the incisional interspaces,

acting as a splint against distracting forces, protecting from environmental contamination, and promoting upregulation in the expression of vascular endothelial growth factor. [17]

Closed incisional negative pressure wound therapy (ciNPWT) has been well described for groin wounds following vascular surgeries, [18] knee and hip arthroplasties, [19] abdominoplasty incisions, [20] breast surgeries, [21] and abdominal wall reconstruction, [22] morbidly obese woman following cesarean section. [23] To the best of our knowledge application of ciNPWT at flap suture line following soft tissue reconstructive surgery has not been described previously.

The aim of the present study was to assess the closed Incisional Negative Pressure Wound Therapy at Flap Suture Line. [24]

Material & Methods

A retrospective analysis for the duration of 12 months of patients who underwent ciNPWT at the flap suture line was included in the study at department of Plastic Surgery, Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, Bihar, India. 30 patients were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria

- Selected high-risk patients who underwent complex reconstruction (pedicled or free flap).
- Patients with soft tissue defects and underlying deep incisional/organ SSI, persistent dead space following flap coverage, chronic osteomyelitis.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients in whom NPWT was used for relieving flap congestion were excluded from the study.

Methodology

Patients also underwent initial debridement and appropriate antibiotic therapy before flap coverage. NPWT was either applied in the operation theater immediately after the flap procedure or within 24 to 48 hours following the procedure. NPWT was applied for patients in whom we anticipated complications of persistent dead space/wound drainage at the recipient site in spite of an appropriate flap cover. The suspicion of dead space was based on clinical examination. Whenever the volume of flap was falling short of the defect's volume, a persistent dead space was diagnosed. The recipient site wound was closed completely with the flap cover in all the patients. The skin suturing was done with longer intervals (1.5–2 cm) to facilitate the effect of NPWT. A 2 to 3 cm wide sponge was cut and applied over the entire suture line adjacent to the flap and connected to the device set at continuous -100 mm Hg pressure. In a patient in whom flap cover was done over the repaired femoral artery, the pressure was set at -50 mm Hg as described by Berger et al.²⁴ This method allows flap monitoring through the transparent adhesive dressing. The dressing is changed after 3 to 4 days. NPWT dressing was reapplied if there was a suspicion of persistent dead space or edematous flap/surrounding skin. In one of the patients, NPWT was continued for 3 weeks because of persistent lymphorrhoea from the groin wound following femoral artery repair. Once the NPWT was discontinued, regular dressings were done.

Results

Table 1: Basic information, demographic characteristics and laboratory indices of patients

		Control Group, n = 20	NPWT Group, n = 10	p value
Age, year		54.6±8.2	53.4±8.8	0.782
Gender, n (%)				>0.92
Male		14(70)	7(70)	
Female		6(30)	3(30)	
ASA grading				0.336
I		6(30)	0	
II		10(50)	8(80)	
III		4(20)	2(20)	
Operation time, minute		266.4±40.6	284.6±30.6	0.432
Bleeding, mL		378.6±254.6	316.4±158.6	0.568
Pre-operation	HGB, g/L	13.16±16.4	13.50±8.2	0.720
	ALT	23.5±5.8	25.8±7.5	0.264
	AST	23.7±7.6	21.9±3.4	0.560
	Creatinine, μmol/L	66.4±10.5	63.7±8.2	0.840
	PT, s	11.9±0.6	11.8±1.2	0.820
	APTT, s	32.3±2.8	32.0±2.1	0.786
	D-dimer, μg/mL	0.19±0.02	0.22±0.08	0.316
Hospitalization time, day		31.6±19.7	19.4±1.7	0.048

There were no significant differences between the two groups in terms of patient baseline information such as age, gender, ASA classification, and preoperative laboratory indices (including haemoglobin, alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase, creatinine, prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, and D-dimer).

Table 2: Postoperative flap manifestations of injured blood supply and wound major complications

	Control Group	NPWT Group	p value
Injured blood supply	9(45)	0	0.055
Epidermal blisters	0	0	
Abnormal color	3(15)	0	0.560
Cold temperature	1(5)	0	1.000
Swelling	5(25)	0	0.550
Major complications	12(60)	0	0.018
Exudation	11(55)	0	0.049
Infection	5(25)	0	0.535
Non-healing	3(15)	0	0.530
Dehiscence ASEPSIS score	1(5)	0	10.001
0-10	1(5)	4(57.2)	
11-20	5(25)	3(42.9)	
21-30	9(45)	-	
31-40	3(15)	-	
>41	1(5)	-	

Within the NPWT group, all patients obtained scores below 20 score. Conversely, within the Control group, a significant majority of patients demonstrated ASEPSIS scores surpassing 20 score.

Table 3: Postoperative assessment of the therapeutic outcome by LEFS, VAS and ADL score

	Control Group	NPWT Group	p value
Preoperative LEFS	52.5±1.8	53.4±1.7	0.384
Postoperative LEFS	48.1±2.6	51.7±1.4	0.004
ΔLEFS score	-2.4±2.1	0.44±0.96	0.007
Preoperative VAS	5.5±0.9	5.3±0.8	0.535
Postoperative VAS	5.0±1.7	6.9±1.1	0.018
ΔVAS score	-0.54±1.8	1.6±0.53	0.001
Preoperative ADLS	69.7±2.6	70.3±2.7	0.640
Postoperative ADLS	71.3±3.1	74.4±2.9	0.048
ΔADLS	1.2±1.8	4.6±2.4	0.003

There was no statistical difference in ADLS scores, LEFS scores, and VAS scores between the two groups.

Discussion

Conventional NPWT is well-known for its role in the management of most of the open acute and chronic wounds. [25] The direct benefits of NPWT are: (a) maintaining moist and warm environment for wound healing provided by the semipermeable adhesive dressing, (b) reducing wound edema by providing pressure gradient between the wound and the suction canister thereby, draining the fluid from the wound bed and the interstitial space, (c) the wound deformation leads to approximation of the wound edges together, skin graft/flap apposition to the wound bed, (d) the wound dehiscence risk is reduced by reduction of lateral strain at the suture site. [26] The tissue deformation is also a stimulus for the remodeling of tissues. [27] The indirect benefits promoting wound healing are augmented blood supply, reduction of inflammation, decreased bacterial burden. [28]

There were no significant differences between the two groups in terms of patient baseline information such as age, gender, ASA classification, and preoperative laboratory indices (including haemoglobin, alanine transaminase, aspartate transaminase, creatinine, prothrombin time, activated partial thromboplastin time, and D-dimer). It is evident that the healing of the flap following the implantation of 3D-printed prostheses is particularly crucial. [29] Firstly, if the flap heals poorly or becomes infected, it can result in the prostheses not being covered. This can greatly affect the patients' limb function and may necessitate further surgery or even amputation. [30,31] Furthermore, long-term treatment can easily lead to psychological problems of patients. The discrepancy between the actual treatment situation and the expected efficacy may cause a serious psychological burden for patients and endanger their mental state. [32,33]

Within the NPWT group, all patients obtained scores below 20 score. Conversely, within the

Control group, a significant majority of patients demonstrated ASEPSIS scores surpassing 20 score. There was no statistical difference in ADLS scores, LEFS scores, and VAS scores between the two groups. Moreover, NPWT enhances blood flow around the wound, and this increased blood supply accelerates the clearance of metabolic waste generated during the cell healing process, while ensuring the provision of nutrients to promote wound healing. [34,35] Negative pressure suction also improves the degree of edema in the surrounding tissues of the wound by promoting lymphatic reflux, increases the formation rate of granulation tissue, and avoids contact between the wound and the external environment, thereby maintaining a relatively sterile wound. [36,37] Additionally, NPWT can reduce the relative displacement of the wound edge and provide a more stable wound healing environment through mechanical stability and appropriate pressure on the wound. [38] Role of NPWT in preventing bacterial migration into the wound following cardiac surgery was hypothesized by Grauhan et al [39] These advantages of cNPWT are also helpful in a reconstructive surgeon's practice in complicated wounds after flap cover.

Conclusion

Closed incisional NPWT decreases the untoward effects of dead space following the reconstruction of complex wounds. The incidence of SSI and wound gaping can be reduced.

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